

Moretti¹, T. Hosni¹, G. Devescovi², I. Cleenwerck³, V. Venturi², R. Buonauro¹. ¹Dipartimento di Scienze Agrarie e Ambientali, Università degli Studi, Via Borgo XX Giugno 74, 06121 Perugia, Italy. ²International Centre for Genetic Engineering and Biotechnology, Padriciano 99, 34149 Trieste, Italy. ³BCCM/LMG Bacteria Collection, Ghent University, Ghent, Belgium. E-mail: chiara.luce.moretti@unipg.it

Olive knots represent an ideal niche not only for the growth of *Pseudomonas savastanoi* pv. *savastanoi* (Pss) but also for a number of endophytic bacteria such as *Erwinia toletana*, *Pantoea agglomerans* and others belonging to the genus *Burkholderia*, *Hafnia* and *Stenotrophomonas*. In 2003 and 2007, 3 *Erwinia*-like strains were isolated from olive knots collected in Central (Umbria) and South (Apulia) Italy, with 16S rDNA gene sequences that were highly similar (> 99%) to strains CECT 5262 and CECT 5264 isolated in Spain from olive knots and provisionally assigned to *Pantoea oleae*. Since the Italian and Spanish strains showed very high similarity (≥ 88%) in rep-PCR assays, using the primers BOX, ERIC and REP, they were subjected to a polyphasic taxonomic study that included: DNA-DNA hybridisation; DNA base ratio determination; multilocus sequence analysis (MLSA), based on concatenated partial *atpD*, *gyrB*, *infB* and *rpoB* gene sequences; and biochemical characterization. On the basis of the genotypic and phenotypic data, we propose to classify the five Italian and Spanish endophytic bacterial strains from olive knots into a novel species. The name *Erwinia oleae* sp. nov. is suggested. *E. oleae* could collaborate with *Pss* in olive knot disease development as it: i) produces *in vitro* detectable levels of indole-3-acetic acid (IAA); ii) bears genes involved in IAA and cytokinin biosyntheses; iii) increases disease severity when inoculated in olive plants together with *Pss*.

ENDOPHYTIC ASCOMYCOTA IN TEMPERATE BROADLEAF FORESTS: COOPERATION OR CONFLICT?

S. Moricca. Dipartimento di Biotechnologie Agrarie, Sezione di Protezione delle Piante, Università degli Studi, Piazzale delle Cascine 28, 50144 Firenze, Italy. E-mail: salvatore.moricca@unifi.it

Fungal endophytes are common host plant symbionts. There is overwhelming evidence that the plant-endophyte association is ancestral and dominant in nature. The fact that such a long standing partnership is so common and widespread indicates it may well have an evolutionary role. The diversity of mycota inhabiting the internal tissue of plants is very high, but only a few taxa are dominant, with species of Diaporthales and Helotiales that are respectively prominent in angiosperms and in gymnosperms. Whereas the asexual, systemic and vertically-transmitted endophytes of grasses are strong mutualists, the sexually-reproducing, horizontally-transmitted endophytes of woody hosts are usually neutral or more often parasitic. These are opportunistic ascomycetes that can live for most of their lifetime as quiescent microthalli in the internal plant tissue, but are also able to resume growth, sporulate and cause disease when the host tree is weakened by other factors. We have been testing such hypothesis by investigating the trophic modes and behavioural ecology of some ascomycota dominating in Mediterranean broadleaf forests, namely *Apiognomonia quercina*, *Biscogniauxia mediterranea*, and several *Botryosphaeria* species. Our results demonstrate that the symbiosis between these microorganisms and their hosts is based on a balanced antagonism, which is labile and dynamic in time. These fungi alternate between a temporally undefined, cryptic existence within their hosts and a parasitic lifestyle, with aggressive colonization of host tissues and organs when plant physiology and performance are impaired by environmental stresses, like

water deficiency. When such conditions occur these endophytes accelerate natural organ senescence and spread contagiously, triggering tree dieback and death.

GRAPEVINE RUPESTRIS STEM PITTING-ASSOCIATED VIRUS: AN INDEXING TRIAL TO FURTHER EVALUATE THE ROLE OF GENETIC VARIANTS IN THE AETIOLOGY OF VEIN NECROSIS. C. Pirollo¹, M. Morelli¹, H. Bouyahia², M. Della Bartola², P. Casati³, A. Minafra⁴, A. Matarazzi², P.A. Bianco³, D. Boscia⁴. ¹Dipartimento di Protezione delle Piante e Microbiologia Applicata, Università degli Studi "Aldo Moro", Via Amendola 165/A, 70126 Bari, Italy. ²Dipartimento di Coltivazione e Difesa delle Specie Legnose "G. Scaramuzzi", Sezione di Patologia Vegetale, Università degli Studi, Via del Borghetto 80, 56124 Pisa, Italy. ³Dipartimento di Produzione Vegetale, Sezione di Patologia Vegetale, Università degli Studi, Via Celoria 2, 20133 Milano, Italy. ⁴Istituto di Virologia Vegetale del CNR, Via Amendola 165/A, 70126 Bari, Italy. E-mail: d.boscia@ba.ivr.cnr.it

The aim of this study was to further analyse the role of the genetic variability of *Grapevine rupestris stem pitting-associated virus* (GRSPaV) in the induction of vein necrosis (VN) in the indicator 110R. Thirty-one grapevine accessions, belonging to 20 different cultivars of *V. vinifera* or rootstocks from Apulia, Tuscany and Lombardy, were RT-PCR-tested with universal primers designed in the viral coat protein gene. Then, the presence of the three known molecular variants of GRSPaV (GI, GII and GIII) was investigated with three degenerate primer pairs. Infections by single virus variants were detected, as well as a complex pattern of mixed infections. All grape accessions under study were subjected to a standardized indexing protocol to observe the reaction of 110R. Within sixty days, all 110R plants top-grafted with GI-infected accessions showed severe symptoms of VN, confirming the alleged association between VN and the molecular variant GRSPaV-SG1 (Genbank accession No. AY881626). Seven out of nine plants infected by the GII and/or GIII variant, did not show any sign of VN, whereas two accessions formerly classified as infected by GII and/or GIII, showed a clear-cut VN reaction. However, when a new round of PCR was done, also the presence of GI was ascertained in both accessions. This suggests that indexing is still a most useful tool to validate molecular testing, as it reduces the risk of false negatives consequent to lack of detection by nucleic acid-based assays of minor variants present in low titre.

This work was funded by the MIUR - PRIN 2007, project 2007RHMMJH.

STUDY OF THE GENES DIFFERENTIALLY EXPRESSED DURING THE INTERACTION BETWEEN ASPERGILLUS FLAVUS AND ZEA MAYS. M. Punelli¹, M. Reverberi¹, P. Uva², W.I. Mentzen², A. Dolezal³, C. Woloshuk⁴, M. Scarpari¹, A.A. Fabbri¹, C. Fanelli¹, G.A. Payne³. ¹Dipartimento di Biologia Vegetale, Università degli Studi "La Sapienza", Largo Cristina di Svezia 24, 00165 Roma, Italy. ²CRSA Bioinformatica - Polaris, 09010 Pula (CA), Italy. ³North Carolina State University, Department of Plant Pathology, 851 Main Campus Raleigh, NC, USA. ⁴Department of Botany and Plant Pathology, Purdue University, 915 West State Street, West Lafayette, IN 47907, USA. E-mail: marta.punelli@unroma1.it

Aflatoxins are carcinogenic fungal secondary metabolites also produced by *Aspergillus flavus* which are strictly regulated in many countries due to health hazards. Since the interaction with the host (e.g. *Zea mays*) affects aflatoxin biosynthesis, we set up